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Digital marketing to boost dental clinic care

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Abstract

Marketing as a science originated and developed in the 20th century, but has a much longer history and has developed in two directions: the first was the transformation into a business enterprise and the second was the internal management of the business due diligence activities. As for the transition to the company, this includes recent developments. This demonstrates that marketing is a science oriented to meet the needs of consumers, forcing their concept to be dynamic and adapt over the years. It works in conjunction with other areas such as production, research, administration, human resources and accounting. On the other hand, digital marketing has its rise in the 90's and with the passage of time became a facilitator of processes such as customer recruitment and staff. Social networks within the dental area and other companies are a good tool for attracting potential customers and strengthening ties with existing ones. For this to be possible, a strategic plan must be implemented, which will always be directed under the mission, vision and values of our company. And, with the help of new digital trends, developing this plan becomes easier.

Keywords: Marketing; SWOT; Clinic; Mission; Vision; Advertising

1. Introduction

Marketing is consumer-oriented and opens up the context to the community in which it operates. Its conceptualization is dynamic and, over time and the evolution of economic structures, varies in adaptation to the surrounding reality. It is a parallel process to other functions such as production, research, administration, human resources and accounting. At the same time, it must also assume responsibility for any negative effects it may generate. (1) (2)

Digital marketing is an effective tool and a process facilitator for national and international trade where various techniques are used to devise business models and strategies aimed at detecting opportunities in global markets, which requires companies to develop forms of communication and integrate a marketing plan, to this end companies manage to segment their markets and know the social media used in each country, professionals in the field of digital marketing, consider that if a product or service is not found on the Internet it simply does not exist. (3) Social networks like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram are a new way to reach the customer, many times people think that these are the main means to market a product or service, but it is also necessary to have a Website and the support of E-mail Marketing. (2) (4)

Marketing has its appearance and development as a science in the twentieth century, however, its history is older and develops in a double line: the first in relation to its evolution as a business philosophy, and the other as regards the organization of commercial activities within the company. The organization of activities dates back to antiquity, specifically to the early days of trade between Phoenicians and Greeks using commercial and promotional techniques. (3)

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As for evolution as philosophy, it comprises a more recent history. It began more than 200 years ago with the term "consumer sovereignty" introduced by Adam Smith and it was Levitt in 1969 who set the idea stating that the purpose of a company was to "create and maintain a customer". (5)

The term "digital marketing" was used as a definition in the 1990s, referring mainly to advertising. However, with the emergence of new social and mobile tools, it expanded and by the years 2000 and 2010, the concept of creating an experience involving users was gradually being created, which changed his concept of what it is to be a brand customer. (2) (6)

2. Phases of the marketing plan

2.1. Situation analysis

This stage is divided into two aspects, one internal and the other external. The internal one speaks of the own resources and capacities with which we have to achieve the objectives. Here we analyze aspects related to financing (liquidity, profitability, financial resources), production (human resources, raw materials, technological and production capacity) and also the organization of our company (hierarchy, corporate identity, corporate culture). With regard to external analysis we must take into account the economic, social, cultural and also political and legal environment. (7)

2.2. SWOT analysis

All the strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities that may arise in the company or the competition are analyzed and studied here, which will allow us to reflect not only the current situation but the possible future. (8)

2.3. Forecasts

The forecasts to be made must include short, medium and long term forecasts regarding the environment in which we are, the market in which we develop our strategy, the evolution of our purchase and also our own company. (8)

2.4. Choice of strategies

The strategy is the path we will follow and, to be considered as such must have the ability to achieve a competitive advantage, consistency with objectives, balance between the resources of the company and the environment. (9)

2.5. Timing

A well-defined timetable is the one that will allow us to specify those responsible for each action, the tactics of each strategy, who carries them out and when, the quantification of resources and when and where they will be allocated. (8)

2.6. Monitoring and evaluation

In order to calculate the actual effectiveness, it is necessary to evaluate the results each time we progress to correct, redirect or eliminate aspects that do not help us achieve the objectives set. (1) (10)

2.7. Objectives

Objectives can be tangible or intangible. The first are measurable, as is the case of a specific percentage in the increase of sales, the take our product to more places, get loyalty of a specific number of customers, etc. Intangibles, on the other hand, are related to improving the image of the brand and increasing its recognition. (10)

2.7.1. Characteristics of the objectives

What is most pursued with the objectives is the fixing of sales volume or market share with the lowest possible risk. For them the objectives must be feasible (achievable and formulated from a practical and realistic perspective); specific and precise (consistent with company guidelines); over time (adjusted to a strategic plan); consensus (as part of the company's general policy); flexible (adapted to the need of the moment); motivators (must be constituted with an achievable challenge). (9) (11)

2.7.2. Development and selection of strategies

It is the path of action available to the company to achieve the objectives. Strategies must be well defined to place the company in an advantageous position in the market and to face competition, in order to achieve greater profitability to the commercial resources allocated by the company. (7) The process to choose strategies is based on:

- Define the target audience to be reached.
- Carry out the general approach and specific objectives of the different marketing variables.
- Determination of the budget concerned.
- Overall evaluation of the plan taking into account the provisional operation, which is recognized if we obtain the fixed profitability.
- Responsible designation that will be responsible for achieving the marketing plan.

2.8. Action plan

Any objective can be achieved by applying a range of tactics; These define the concrete actions to be implemented in order to achieve the impact of the strategy. This implies having human, technical and economic resources capable of carrying out the marketing plan.(9)

2.9. Budget setting

For marketing management to approve the plan, it must know the quantification of effort expressed in monetary terms. It is not the means to achieve objectives, it is the programme. (3)

2.10. Control system and contingency plan

The last requirement is control, which allows us to know the degree of compliance with objectives as strategies and tactics are applied. The aim is to detect possible failures and deviations with the possible consequences that they generate, with the aim of applying remedies and corrective measures immediately. (3) (11)

2.11. Mission, vision and values

This decision-making is the role and responsibility of managers at all levels of the organization, but the ultimate responsibility lies with senior management. (1)

- Vision: is the result of a search process, resulting in experience and accumulation of information.
- Mission: defines the *raison d'être* of the company, conditioning its activities, providing unity, sense of direction and strategic decision-making guidance. It allows us to clearly identify the market we have, who our customers are and the potential competition. (7) (12)
- Values: the company's philosophy consists of a series of principles based on knowing who we are and in which we believe, our precepts, commitments and responsibilities to the public, both internally and externally. That is, it establishes the framework of relations between the company and its shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, government, society in general, etc. (1)

2.12. Implementation of the marketing plan in the dental clinic

2.12.1. Analysis of the current situation of the clinic

Internal environment analysis: involves the quality of professionals who are part of the clinic, qualified auxiliary staff and the presence of a hierarchical organizational structure. The aim is to create a single identity as a group within the company, which must bear a functional and descriptive name that is related to the organization and the professional. (3) (5) (12)

External environment analysis: identifies the competence of our dental clinic, located in the same sectors or in the same city. In this case we recognize four basic types of competitors, the branded ones (they market products with similar characteristics and benefits); product (they compete over the same class of products, but with different characteristics, benefits and costs); generic products (market different products that solve the same problem or satisfy the same need) and total budget competitors (compete for limited financial resources from the same customers). (3) (7)

SWOT analysis: evidence of weaknesses (unfavourable details about the same aspects discussed in the previous point), opportunities (alliances with different companies, benchmarking with recognized brands, alliances with financial

institutions for ease of payment, innovation with techniques/inputs from abroad or expanding public relations), strengths (favorable details about infrastructure, regulations, marketing, personnel and services) and threats (direct competition that generates stability at the level of the dental clinic.), (13)

Marketing goals and objectives: the objective should be to design a strategic marketing plan for the dental clinic, which contributes to the positioning and knowledge of it in the city where it is located and its respective sector. At this point the company must support the mission and organizational goals and then translate them into objectives. (3) (7)

Marketing strategy: analyzing the current state of the clinic, should focus on implementing a marketing plan that enhances the image and sales of it through marketing focused on product promotion. At this point, having a name that is not similar to the other clinics and that is in the right colors, ensures to attract the attention of potential clients. (6) (7)

Marketing implementation: at this point, the suggested strategies for positioning the clinic should be listed.

Publicity: at the first month of launch, publications should be made about the services, specialists and publicize the dental clinic. Currently this can be done on social networks such as Instagram, Facebook, TikTok with the help of links on them, which redirects the user to the website of our clinic. (11)

Implementation of the website: place the name of the clinic, redirect all publications made from the link to the networks of specialists who make up the clinic team, make paid guidelines once a month offering special services or promotions, follow up with customers to publish their progress in the processes carried out, publish at least 2 times a week showing the service plus, make a video publication with recommendations and oral health tips by specialists and make testimonials on the website. (8) (10)

Public relations: make brochure with corporate identity, visit in person or hold workshops in universities to publicize the portfolio of service, become known in mass media, publish health articles in different digital research journals, participate in events with dental stands or symposia, get strategic allies, establish social networks as the strongest sales channel for services. (10)

Events and experiences: publicizing the national and international participation of the company, and professional profiles. (10)

Sales promotion: create a plus discount to the person who brings a referral and this is effective to acquire a new service. (10)

Direct marketing: use staff or regular users of the clinic as company communicators or constantly send services provided to clients through social networks. (8) (10)

Evaluation and control: to review the behavior of user visits on the website, to inquire by what means the provision of services was known when the consultation was first attended, make calls to clients to measure satisfaction with the services provided, monitor sales for the last 6 months after the launch of the clinic and talk to clients to measure the impact on the perception of the service provided. (8)

3. Conclusions

Marketing has a dynamic concept that adapts with the evolution of economic structures, that is, varies in adaptation to the surrounding reality and, works around the choice of strategies with a well-defined timetable and that is subject to various analyses to achieve an enterprise development.

It is a parallel process to other functions such as production, research, administration, etc. Therefore, responsibility must also be assumed for any negative effects it may generate.

Digital marketing is not only an advertising of a business or company, currently, it is the most accurate way to reach a certain sector that may require our services.

In the case of a dental clinic or office, making proper use of these tools will allow the name of it to be enhanced through various digital spaces and thus increase the uptake and promotion to new customers.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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